

Miraculous Biology

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Abstract: This article provides information about the unique plants and strange creatures on our planet.

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1. Introduction

Rare plants are plants that have a specific function and are rarely found on the planet. One type of rare plant is the wild plant. Wild plants are a miracle of nature. Because where there is a lack of nutrients, they create a strange survival strategy for the plant world, which is to catch and eat live prey. There are about 450 species of this plant, which can be found all over the world.

Poisonous plants - This type of plant can be found in many different conditions. The human race has learned to make unique medicines from many poisonous plants. For example, strophanthus seeds are used to treat heart disease. Toxic sumac juice is used to treat paralysis, rheumatism and a number of other diseases.

The bread tree is a real treasure for the ocean dwellers. Its fruit, which weighs more than 20 kg, is a substitute for bread for the natives. They eat this fruit raw and overcooked. It tastes like wheat bread. The tree bears fruit every year for 70 years. It also produces fabric from the fibrous bark of the tree, paper and hats from the leaves, medicine from the roots, and dye from the bark.

Jenshen is a root man. Ginseng has been used in the East for about 4,000 years. From ancient times the doctors knew that the medicine made from the roots of this plant gives a person strength and youth. The shape of the root also played an important role in Jenshen's popularity. Because this form is reminiscent of human structure, the Chinese called it "jen" - man, "shen" - root.

2. Main part

Smell champions. Bees are champions in the sense of smell. They have developed the ability to perceive and perceive smell 1000 times stronger than humans. Even when the bees are more than 1 km away, they can smell the flowers. Because dogs have a stronger sense of smell than bees, bees can be easily used to detect the presence of explosives or drugs. The main honey harvest season lasts from 8 to 20 days, and at other times of the year, bees prepare for the harvest season. Most honey is produced in the Far East and Siberia. Learn more about bees:

- 1) Every year, 3 times more people die from bee stings than from venomous snake bites.
- 2) One bee has to fly 10 million times from hive to flower and from flower to hive to make 500 g of honey.
- 3) Bees have 5 eyes. 3 eyes are at the top of the head and 2 are at the front.

Snakes. Snakes belong to the class of reptiles and there are more than 2,000 species of them in the world. Snakes live on the ground, under the ground, on top of trees, and in water. They move with their ribs, and when they jump, the skin moves intact. Snakes don't have ears. However, their language can distinguish between different sounds and is very sensitive to sound signals. One of the most venomous snakes is the snake. Its poison is widely used in medicine. Another poisonous snake is the king cobra. The venom of this snake is also used in medicine. The venom of this snake is also extremely dangerous. Because one gram of venom of this snake is enough to kill 150 people. Snakes differ in their type of reproduction. For example, a rattlesnake and a lizard give birth to a live baby without laying eggs. There are some types of snakes that can breed up to 75 at a time. Most snakes reproduce by laying eggs. It is estimated that the most eggs are laid by the Indian python. It can lay up to 107 eggs at a time. Snake eggs are stored in the sun for some time. Sometimes snakes form a ring around their eggs to protect their offspring. As soon as the babies hatch, the mother snake is released. Because snake babies can take care of themselves from birth. Learn more about the snake:

- 1) Snakes do not hear sounds propagating in the air.
- 2) Snake venom can kill an elephant.
- 3) The length of the anaconda reaches 9 m.

4) Snake venom is more expensive than gold.

Lions. Lions are the most famous, yet most atypical representative of the cat family. One of the peculiarities of his life is that he lives in a herd and that male lions are almost incapable of hunting. According to experts, if one lion appears in the savannah, it means that the rest will happen soon. Because the power of lions is in solidarity. There are two types of cats, lions and cheetahs. In lions, this lifestyle is called primate. There may be several pomegranate lions in a herd (often brothers). If they are more than one, the dominant is separated and its superiority is recognized by all without resistance. He eats the prey first, mates first with the female, and is the first to attack the enemy lion, which has invaded the Pride area. On average, the African Lions' Pride consists of 13 animals. This number can go up to 40. It is said that the roar of a lion is the most horrible of all wild animals. In most cases, the roar of a lion can be heard from a distance of 8-9 km. Lions usually roar at sunset, signaling to other creatures that the space they occupy is busy. Lions have an average lifespan of 15 to 17 years and can live up to 30 years at most. The length of the pomegranate lion, excluding the tail, reaches 180 - 240 cm. Body weight can range from 180 to 230 kg. Asian lions are relatively small: a large pomegranate weighs 160 to 190 kg, and a female pomegranate weighs 120 kg. Learn more about lions: 1) Lions only have a way in the distance. 2) Lions don't know how to roar until they are 2 years old. 3) The beak of a lion is as different as a human fingerprint. They don't have the same nose or the same path. Strange features of the human body. The physiological changes that take place in the human body from the womb to the grave are undoubtedly rich in mysteries. Of course, scientists still have a lot of unresolved puzzles. But there are also many discoveries that show how many strange properties there are in the human body. Of the 2 billion people, only one lives more than 120 years. In a lifetime, a person's skin changes 1,000 times, and each finger bends 25 million times in a lifetime. An adult inhales and exhales about 23,000 times a day.

The size of a human heart is about the size of a fist. The weight of an adult heart is 220-260 g. The pressure exerted by the heart has the power to lift our blood to a height of 9 m. When we sneeze, all the functions of our body, even the heart, stop. The human brain produces 100,000 chemical reactions per second. At birth, the brain contains 14 billion cells, a number that does not increase until the end of life. Again, after the age of 25, the number of cells decreases by 100,000 per day. It takes 70 cells to read a page. After the age of 40, brain degradation accelerates sharply, and after the age of 50, the neuronal and brain size decreases. There is a saying in Italy: "In countries where apricots are grown, scientists grow more." Because the brains of people who ate white apricots as a child work better than others. Not only human fingerprints but also tongue marks have a wonderful feature. The theory is that coded locks can be made based on language traces. The only problem is that we can't hold our tongue motionless. This organ is active even when we are asleep. Human weight is constantly changing. For example, if you remove only carbon dioxide from the body, you will lose 75-85 g of weight in a day. Yawning is not just a sign of insomnia. According to scientists, this physiological process accelerates brain activity.

3. Interesting facts:

- 1) Leukocytes live in the human body for 2-4 days, erythrocytes for 3-4 days.
- 2) Nerve impulses in the human body travel at a speed of about 90 m per second.
- 3) 10% of men and 8% of women are bald.
- 4) The right lung holds more air than the left.
- 5) Human DNA has 80,000 genes.
- 6) 50% of our bones are made up of water.
- 7) A baby has 300 bones in its body and an adult has 206 bones.

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